

Indigenous traditional knowledge, biodiversity conservation and nature-based businesses

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Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities are renowned as nature custodians. This is not coincidental. Numerous studies worldwide have shown that indigenous lifeways are intrinsically connected to Mother Nature. The Sto:lo Indigenous People of Vancouver, Canada, use the same word to mean both "umbilical cord" and "Mother Earth," highlighting our connection to the earth in the same way we are connected to our mothers. The Maasai believe the land is alive; it is seen as dead or dying when bare, symbolizing the end of life and sadness. To prevent the dying of the land, indigenous customary laws and knowledge systems play a critical role in treating and restoring it. However, these traditional systems are at risk as we embrace new technologies and governance systems to manage our lands. Indigenous traditional knowledge and systems have shaped the environment we see today and deserve respect.

Most, if not all, nature-based businesses depend on thriving ecosystems. It is easy to forget the custodians who have maintained this stability. In most cases, investors seek control, starting with the legal ownership of the land, often dispossessing the owners without their Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC). This leads to the criminalization of indigenous peoples and local communities' actions on the land. Full and effective participation of indigenous peoples and local communities in establishing any businesses ensures their rights are respected and assures access to and use of natural resources. Many businesses do not require land ownership but access to resources with the consent of the indigenous peoples. For example, a wind power project only needs access to the wind, allowing communities to retain their land rights. Investors should be aware that the lands they invest in are homes and sources of livelihoods for people. In conservation and tourism, many ecosystems have a long history of people coexisting with nature. This needs recognition and support.

Indigenous knowledge is precious and exceptionally important to its owners. Documenting this knowledge is a step in the right direction. However, documentation is often done by professionals in their careers, turning indigenous knowledge into new innovations owned by those who learned from indigenous communities. This is piracy and extractive. Such documentation does not secure this knowledge for future generations. To ensure indigenous traditional knowledge is documented for its intended people, the research and documentation process must fully respect the full and effective participation of indigenous people and local communities. Documentation of this knowledge should respect the owners and encourage community action research that involves the indigenous peoples and local communities at all levels. This way, the community can provide the right knowledge that serves their needs, not the external interests of researchers. Indigenous knowledge is a whole undocumented science that needs recognition and respect. A significant challenge is that people use scientific knowledge to prove indigenous knowledge.

To overcome these barriers, indigenous traditional knowledge should be given proper recognition. As a science, this knowledge should be taught in the same way as other knowledge systems. Traditional knowledge transfer systems have been affected by modern activities. Learning by doing and practicing indigenous knowledge has been the best transfer system for indigenous knowledges. The bond of interaction between the young and the old has been broken by other knowledge systems and technologies where children now discuss school syllabus, watch television, and play computer games instead of listening to elders' storytelling.